

**Science
Mesh**

Science Mesh Glossary

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Term	Description
AAI	Authentication and authorisation infrastructure.
Central Database	All information about the participating sites is stored in a central place. This includes general information about a site (e.g., its name, homepage and contact details), as well as a list of its services.
Central Component	The collection of central services in the Science Mesh.
Enterprise File Sync- and Share (EFSS)	Is a software and service for organising digital files, share them in a controlled manner inside and outside user's organisation, store them in a server infrastructure and synchronise them across various devices.
Executive Module	The EM serves as a service discovery interface for the users, providing a WAYF-like interface for sharing by invitation that allows the target user to identify the target system; in a similar manner also for target applications for scenarios like "open my file in a remote application." The EM enforces sharing/application access/data transfer policies and signs requests to approve they are compliant with the policy.
Healthy	A service is considered to be in a healthy state if it is up (i.e., the service is running and can be reached from the outside) as well as functioning correctly; the exact meaning of the latter depends on the service type and is determined by automated tests.
Inter Operability Platform (IOP)	Middleware that allows the linking of storage and application platforms. More information may be found here .
Mesh Metadata	A description of Sites, their technical and administrative contacts, supported services, service endpoints, technical information necessary to use their services and other information.
Operational Team (OT)	A team responsible for operations of centralised components in the Mesh and technical and communication procedures regarding Site membership.
Science Mesh Policy Framework Constitution	A document describing the governance structure of the Science Mesh. The document may be found here .
Science Mesh	Is an infrastructure federating EFSS systems to allow easy and controlled sharing of resources such as data (files and folders) and applications.
Science Mesh Site Declaration	The declaration signed by Sites on joining the

Term	Description
Science Mesh Operational Practice Statement	Science Mesh. Documentation of technical requirements, tools, and procedures adopted by the Science Mesh to facilitate its operations.
Science Mesh Executive Board (SMEB)	A body nominated by the sponsors of the Science Mesh service and responsible for ratifying certain decisions of the SMSG.
Science Mesh Steering Group (SMSG)	A body consisting of representatives of member Sites, having an oversight role in the Science Mesh infrastructure.
Site	Is a single partner participating in the Science Mesh (organisational entity such as a national or regional e-infrastructure, university and/or institute) and running certain EFSS systems and related services.
Site Policy	A set of documents describing Terms and Conditions of using the Site, Privacy policy etc.
Site Representative	A person who acts on behalf of the Site within the context of the Science Mesh.
Sponsors	The Sites financing operations of Science Mesh central components, typically through a grant and/or project.
WAYF	Where Are You From. In the Science Mesh this is a service offered by the Executive Module to let the target User where resources are going to be shared to select his home EFSS.
User	An individual that uses the services offered by an EFSS run by a Site.